
HBAT 2: A Python Package to Analyse Hydrogen Bonds and Other Non-covalent Interactions in Macromolecular Structures

Abhishek Tiwari¹ *

1 Independent Researcher

* abhishek@abhishek-tiwari.com

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Software

- [Code Repository](#)
- [Documentation](#)
- [PyPI Package](#)

1 Abstract

Hydrogen bonds and other non-covalent interactions play a crucial role in maintaining the structural integrity and functionality of biological macromolecules such as proteins and nucleic acids. Accurate identification and analysis of these interactions are essential for understanding molecular recognition, protein folding, and drug design. HBAT¹ (Hydrogen Bond Analysis Tool) is software for analysing hydrogen bonds and other weak interactions in macromolecular structures. This paper presents HBAT 2, an updated Python reimplementa-tion of the original HBAT tool published in 2007. HBAT 2 is a Python package for automated analysis of hydrogen bonds and other non-covalent interactions in macromolecular structures available in Protein Data Bank (PDB) file format. The software identifies and analyses traditional hydrogen bonds, weak hydrogen bonds, halogen bonds, X-H... π , π - π stacking, and n \rightarrow π^* interactions using geometric criteria. It also detects cooperativity and anticooperativity chains and renders them as 2D visualisations. The latest version offers improved cross-platform tkinter-based graphical user interface (GUI), a web-based interface², a simple command-line interface (CLI), and a developer-friendly API, making it accessible to users with different computational backgrounds.

2 Keywords

Python, structural biology, hydrogen bonds, molecular interactions, protein structures, bioinformatics, non-covalent interactions, PDB analysis

3 Introduction

Hydrogen bonds and other non-covalent interactions are fundamental to protein structure, stability, and function. With over 200,000 structures in the Protein Data Bank [1], there is an increasing need for automated tools to analyse these interactions systematically.

The landscape of hydrogen bond analysis tools is diverse but fragmented. Classic tools like HBPLUS [2] and HBexplore [3] pioneered automated H-bond detection but

¹<https://hbat.abhishek-tiwari.com>

²<https://hbat-web.abhishek-tiwari.com>

lack modern interfaces and support for a diverse range of interactions. More recent tools serve specialized niches: PLIP [4] and Arpeggio [5] excel at protein-ligand interactions but are web-based without standalone GUI options; HBonanza [6], HBCalculator [7], and BRIDGE2 [8] focus on molecular dynamics trajectories rather than static structures; MDAnalysis [9], GROMACS [10], and AMBER [11] provide H-bond analysis within larger MD suites. Tools like VMD [12] and ChimeraX [13] offer interactive hydrogen bond visualisation but limited statistical analysis. ProteinTools [14] provides web-based network analysis but lacks cross-platform desktop capabilities.

Despite this ecosystem, there remains a gap for a comprehensive and reliable cross-platform desktop tool that: (1) analyses diverse interaction types beyond canonical hydrogen bonds, (2) provides both graphical and command-line interfaces for different user workflows, (3) identifies potential cooperativity, (4) integrates seamlessly with the existing scientific ecosystem, and (5) supports flexible parameter customization with domain-specific presets.

The original HBAT [15] was developed in Perl/Tk with a Windows-only GUI, limiting its adoption in modern computational environments. HBAT 2 addresses these limitations by providing a modern, Python implementation that integrates seamlessly with contemporary structural biology workflows. The software is particularly valuable for researchers in structural biology, computational chemistry, and drug design who need detailed analysis of molecular interactions.

Figure 1. The latest update to HBAT 2 uses tkinter to provide a cross-platform graphical user interface (GUI)

4 Methods

4.1 Implementation

HBAT 2 employs a modular architecture with separate components for PDB parsing, geometric analysis, statistical computation, and visualisation. The core analysis engine uses efficient nearest-neighbor searching with configurable distance cutoffs, followed by geometric filtering based on distance and angular criteria.

4.1.1 Structure Preparation

HBAT 2 uses PDBFixer [16], [17] and OpenBabel [18] to automatically enhance macromolecular structures by adding missing atoms, converting residues, and cleaning up structural issues. These capabilities are particularly valuable when working with crystal structures missing hydrogen atoms, low-resolution structures with incomplete side chains, structures containing non-standard amino acid residues, and structures with unwanted ligands or contaminants.

4.1.2 Interaction Detection

The software implements the same fundamental geometric approach as the original version [15] but with optimised algorithms and improved handling. HBAT 2 analyses a broad spectrum of interactions including:

- Hydrogen bonds (O-H \cdots O, N-H \cdots O, N-H \cdots N, C-H \cdots O)
- Halogen bonds (C-X \cdots Y where X=F,Cl,Br,I)
- X-H \cdots π interactions with aromatic systems
- π - π stacking [19], [20]
- Carbonyl-carbonyl n \rightarrow π^* interactions [21], [22]
- n \rightarrow π^* interactions [23]

This comprehensive approach addresses the growing recognition of weak interactions' importance in protein structure and stability [24], [25], [26].

4.1.3 Cooperativity Analysis

HBAT 2 offers two ways to visualise hydrogen bond networks: NetworkX [27]/Matplotlib [28] and GraphViz [29]. Unlike tools that provide only basic visualisation (VMD, ChimeraX) or focus solely on MD trajectory dynamics (BRIDGE2, HBonanza), HBAT 2 emphasises cooperativity chains and network topology in static structures with customizable layouts and high-resolution export (PNG, SVG, PDF). Cooperativity analysis and visualisation support in HBAT 2 builds on top of original HBAT [15] and HBNG [30].

4.1.4 3D Visualization

HBAT 2 integrates 3Dmol.js [31] for interactive 3D visualization of molecular structures and detected interactions. This JavaScript-based viewer is available both on the web server ³ and as a widget in Jupyter notebooks, enabling researchers to interactively explore structures without requiring separate visualization software. The 3D viewer

³<https://hbat-web.abhishek-tiwari.com>

Figure 2. HBAT 2 analysis workflow showing the complete pipeline from PDB input to multiple output formats

highlights detected interactions with customizable color schemes and allows users to rotate, zoom, and inspect specific interaction geometries. In Jupyter notebooks, the visualization widget can be embedded directly alongside analysis code, facilitating reproducible computational workflows and interactive data exploration. This integration bridges the gap between automated analysis and manual structural inspection, allowing users to validate detected interactions visually and gain intuitive understanding of complex interaction networks. Shortcuts to launch example Jupyter notebooks with Google Colab - a hosted Jupyter Notebook service that requires no setup to use and provides free access to computing resources - are also provided⁴.

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Figure 3. C-H... π interaction between A:ALA:20 \rightarrow A:TYR:25 of PDB Structure 6RSA

⁴<https://github.com/abhishektiwari/hbat/tree/main/notebooks>

4.1.5	Parameter Presets	95
	Built-in parameter sets optimised for different experimental conditions (high-resolution X-ray, NMR, membrane proteins, drug design) address a common challenge in hydrogen bond analysis. While other tools require manual parameter specification, HBAT’s preset system makes it accessible to experimental structural biologists while maintaining flexibility for computational experts.	96 97 98 99 100
4.1.6	Output Formats	101
	Multiple export formats (text, CSV, JSON) enable integration with downstream analysis pipelines and statistical software. Combined with optional PDBFixer and OpenBabel integration for automated hydrogen addition, HBAT 2 provides a complete workflow from raw PDB files to publication-ready analyses.	102 103 104 105
4.2	Operation	106
	HBAT 2 requires Python 3.8 or higher and runs on Windows, macOS, and Linux. The software can be installed via pip (pip install hbat) or conda (conda install -c hbat hbat). Optional dependencies include GraphViz for advanced network visualization and PDBFixer/OpenBabel for structure preparation.	107 108 109 110
	A web-based interface is available at https://hbat-web.abhishek-tiwari.com providing immediate access without local installation. The web server supports all core analysis features including structure preparation, interaction detection, and cooperativity analysis with interactive visualization. Users can upload PDB files up to 1MB and download results in multiple formats (CSV, JSON, and fixed PDB files).	111 112 113 114 115
5	Use Cases	116
	HBAT 2 extends the impact of the original tool by providing modern capabilities across diverse research areas. Since its initial publication, HBAT has been employed in numerous studies spanning structural biology, drug discovery, and clinical genomics.	117 118 119
5.1	Structure-based drug design	120
	Analysis of protein-ligand interactions including hydrogen bonds and halogen bonds crucial for binding affinity and rational inhibitor design.	121 122
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Díaz-Cervantes et al. characterized protein-ligand interactions for anticancer compounds targeting ABL kinase [32]• Ravindran et al. analyzed cardiovascular disease receptors with Withaferin A metabolite interactions [33]• Zhou et al. predicted EGFR drug resistance based on hydrogen bond patterns [34]• Russo Krauss et al. elucidated thrombin-aptamer interactions crucial for anticoagulant design [35]	123 124 125 126 127 128 129
5.2	Protein engineering	130
	Identification of stabilizing interactions for rational mutagenesis to improve enzyme thermostability, activity, and specificity.	131 132

The screenshot shows the HBAT 2 - Web Server interface. The browser address bar displays 'hbat-web.abhishek-tiwari.com'. The page header includes a menu icon, the HBAT 2 logo, the title 'HBAT 2 - Web Server', and links for 'Cite', 'Docs', and 'GitHub'. The main content area features a progress bar with four steps: 'Upload PDB File' (checked), 'Configure Parameters & Run' (checked), 'View Results' (active), and 'Export Results' (disabled). Below the progress bar is a navigation menu with tabs for 'SUMMARY', 'HYDROGEN BONDS (104)', 'PI INTERACTIONS (19)', 'CARBONYL N→Π* (35)', 'N→Π* (1)', and 'COOPERATIVITY (23)'. The 'HYDROGEN BONDS (104)' tab is selected. A search bar contains the text 'UVC'. Below the search bar is a table of hydrogen bond data.

3D View	Donor Residue	Donor Atom	Hydrogen Atom	Acceptor Residue	Acceptor Atom	H...A (Å)	Angle (°)	D...A (Å)
	B:DOD:92	O	D2	B:UVC:1	O3V	2.04	144.8	2.89
	B:DOD:95	O	D1	B:UVC:1	O2V	2.48	122.8	3.11

At the bottom of the table, there are two buttons: 'Back' and 'Next'.

Figure 4. HBAT 2 is also available as a web server and supports analysis of PDB files up to 1MB.

- Wang et al. identified weak C-H $\cdots\pi$ and C-H \cdots O interactions in thermostable α -amylase variants, revealing that mutations in central β -strands can enhance enzyme performance [36] 133-135
- Fournier et al. characterized hydrogen bonding networks essential for halide specificity in vanadium iodoperoxidases [37] 136-137

5.3 Molecular dynamics analysis 138

Statistical analysis of interaction patterns across molecular dynamics trajectories and time-resolved structural ensembles. 139-140

- Huang, Massa, and Karle (Nobel laureate Jerome Karle) characterized hydrogen bonds in vesicular stomatitis virus nucleoprotein, enabling quantum mechanical energy calculations critical for understanding viral RNA encapsulation [38] 141-143
- Jayaprakash et al. analyzed glycoprotein-lectin interactions for ER quality control mechanisms [39] 144-145
- Barzegar and Tohidifar investigated Hoogsteen H-bond stabilization in G-quadruplex DNA nanomotors [40] 146-147

5.4 Crystallographic studies 148

Quality assessment and validation of refined structures through detailed hydrogen bond network analysis. 149-150

- Daubner et al. revealed SRSF2's novel recognition mechanism for guanine and cytosine through syn-anti conformational flexibility in NMR structures [41] 151-152

5.5 Comparative structural analysis 153

Systematic comparison of interaction networks across protein families to understand structural effects of mutations and polymorphisms. 154-155

- Kavitha and Mohanapriya identified deleterious TOP2A mutations in ovarian cancer [42] 156-157
- Khan and Ansari predicted highly deleterious E17K mutation in AKT1 gene [43] 158
- Khan et al. characterized functional SNPs in Axin 1 gene associated with colorectal cancer [44] 159-160
- Abdulazeez et al. identified rs61742690 (S783N) SNP as target for disrupting BCL11A-mediated fetal-to-adult globin switching [45] 161-162
- AbdulAzeez and Borgio analyzed deleterious nsSNPs in HBA1 gene associated with α -thalassemia [46] 163-164

The software's preset configurations and flexible parameter system make it accessible to both computational experts and experimental structural biologists. Since its original publication, HBAT has been cited in numerous studies of protein structure and molecular recognition [15]. 165-167-168

Figure 5. An example visualisation of potential cooperativity chain generated by HBAT 2 software for Protein Data Bank (PDB) entry 4X21

6 Discussion

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HBAT 2 represents a significant modernization of the original HBAT tool, addressing key limitations while preserving its core functionality. The transition to Python and addition of cross-platform GUI support removes barriers to adoption that limited the original Perl/Tk implementation. The expanded repertoire of interaction types and cooperativity analysis capabilities position HBAT 2 as a comprehensive tool for modern structural biology research.

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The modular architecture and well-documented API facilitate integration into larger computational pipelines and enable customization for specialized research needs. The preset parameter system, informed by best practices from structural biology literature, lowers the barrier to entry for experimental researchers while maintaining the flexibility required by computational specialists.

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6.1 Limitations

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Current limitations of HBAT 2 include: (1) analysis focuses on static structures without accounting for conformational dynamics or solvent effects, (2) interaction detection relies on geometric criteria alone without energy calculations, which may miss energetically unfavorable but geometrically valid interactions, (3) network visualization performance may degrade with very large structures containing >5,000 interactions, (4) preset parameters are optimized primarily for protein structures and may require adjustment for other biomolecules such as DNA/RNA complexes, and (5) cooperativity analysis identifies potential chains based on topology but does not quantify cooperative energetic effects.

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Future development will focus on enhanced support for large biomolecular complexes, integration with molecular dynamics analysis workflows, and machine learning-based interaction prediction to complement geometric criteria.

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7 Data Availability

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No new data were generated for this software tool article. Example PDB files used for validation are available from the Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org/>).

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8 Software Availability

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- HBAT web server available on: <https://hbat-web.abhishek-tiwari.com/>
- HBAT documentation available on: <https://hbat.abhishek-tiwari.com/>
- Source code available from: <https://github.com/abhishektiwari/hbat>
- PyPI Package available from: <https://pypi.org/project/hbat/>
- Archived source code: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.XXXXXXX>
- License: [MIT License](#)

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9 Competing Interests

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No competing interests were disclosed.

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